

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D8.3. Recycling process flow design

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

Document details	
Project Information	
Project Acronym/ Name:	SPINMATE
Project URL:	www.spinmate.eu
Project Type:	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-05 (Manufacturing technology development for solid-state batteries (SSB, Generations 4a - 4b batteries) (Batteries Partnership))
Grant Agreement No.:	101069712
Project Start Date:	01/08/2022
Project End Date:	31/07/2026
Document details	
Work package:	WP8
Deliverable:	D8.3. Recycling process flow design
Due date of Deliverable:	31/01/2024
Actual Submission Date:	31/01/2024
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	Report Author (s): Javier Mayorga, Gabriel Hidalgo (ABEE)
Reviewed by:	Inês Ribeiro (INEGI); Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha, Zeynep Aktosun (ABEE); Simon Ziegler, Andreas Gronbach (ISCF)
Revision:	V4
Dissemination Level:	Public

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
V0	22.12.2023	First draft of the deliverable.	Javier Mayorga (ABEE)
V1	28.12.2023	General review, corrections, and propose for additional information.	Inês Ribeiro (INEGI)
V2	19.01.2024	Review the technical parts, minor corrections, and propose for additional Information.	Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha, Zeynep Aktosun (ABEE)
V3	23.01.2024	Technical review	Simon Ziegler, Andreas Gronbach (ISCF)
V4	26.01.2024	Final draft	Javier Mayorga, Gabriel Hidalgo (ABEE)

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the SPINMATE Consortium, 2021
 This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Glossary and Abbreviations	
AAM	Anode Active Material
CAM	Cathode Active Material
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
DMF	Dimethylformamide
DMSO	Dimethyl Sulfoxide
EC	Ethyl Carbonate
EoL	End-of-Life Batteries
EU	European Union
H₂S	Sulfide Hydrogen
HF	Hydrofluoric Acid
IL	Ionic Liquids
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
Li₂C₂O₄	Li Oxalate
Li₂CO₃	Li Carbonate
LIB	Lithium-Ion Battery
LiM	Lithium Metal
LiPF₆	Lithium Hexafluorophosphate
LMOs	Lithium Transition Metal Oxides
NMC811	LiNi _{0.8} Mn _{0.1} Co _{0.1} O ₂
PFD	Process Flow Diagram
PEL	Permissible Exposure Limit
PLS	Pregnant Liquid Solution
PO	Polyolefin
PVDF-HP	Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene)
SEI	Solid-Electrolyte Interphase
SSBs	Solid-State Batteries
SX	Solvent Extraction
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Contents

Executive Summary.....	7
1. Introduction	8
2. SPINMATE cell chemistry and characteristics.....	8
3. LIBs recycling state-of-art overview.....	10
4. SSBs recycling.....	15
4.1 Potential recycling approaches	17
4.2 Recycling process flow definition	26
5. Conclusion.....	29
6. References	30

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Structure of a SPINMATE monolayer cell.....	10
Figure 2 - Global battery demand.....	10
Figure 3 - Forecast scrap production (a) and EoL LIBs generation (b).....	11
Figure 4 EoL EV batteries and production scrap available for recycling	11
Figure 5 - recycling targets set in the Battery Regulation	12
Figure 6- LIBs recycling routes.....	13
Figure 7 - Relithiation process scheme.....	14
Figure 8 - CAM vs constituents cost.....	15
Figure 9 - Li metal reaction with nitrogen.....	16
Figure 10 - Manual disassembly approach scheme.....	18
Figure 11 - Mechanical pre-processing approach scheme.....	18
Figure 12 - Patented process scheme for LiM recovery from LiM-polymer cells	19
Figure 13 - LiM conversion process scheme.....	21
Figure 14 - Electrolyte recovery process scheme.....	23
Figure 15 - Downstream process flow scheme.....	24
Figure 16 - Recycling PFD based on manual disassembly approach.....	27
Figure 17 - Recycling process flow diagram of Approach 2.a and 2.b.....	28

List of Tables

Table 1 - Amount of H ₂ S generated from different sulfide-based.....	9
Table 2 Recycling targets for SPINMATE cells.....	12
Table 3 - SoA LIBs recycling processes and limitations for SSBs.....	16
Table 4 - Solubility of Li salts in water at room temperature.....	20
Table 5- Potential solvents for PVDF-HFP.....	21
Table 6 - List of extractants and potential recovery routes.....	25
Table 7 - Resins selected for the ion-exchange process.....	26

Executive Summary

This document describes the activities conducted under the SPINMATE project to define a novel recycling process flow for the solid-state batteries developed in the project. It contains results obtained in *Task 8.4 Recycling process flow design and process optimization*, within work package 8 (WP8) “Environmental and cost impact assessment through the value chain” .

This deliverable establishes a conceptual recycling process flow for SPINMATE cells that will be experimentally optimized and proved in the subsequent task (T8.5. Experimental Recycling process.). The process design is based on the cell chemistry, literature research and inputs from partners working on the development of the cell materials in WP3.

1. Introduction

WP8 addresses environmental, economic, and recycling aspects of SPINMATE projects through five tasks. The recycling activities are grouped in tasks 8.4 and 8.5. Task 8.4 focuses on the conceptual design of the recycling process flow, while Task 8.5 will experimentally assess the defined recycling process flow on the cells developed during the project and will provide the requirements for future recycling and the recommendations for upscaling.

Deliverable 8.3 shows the result from the activities carried out within M3-M18 in task 8.4. The objective of Deliverable 8.3 is to develop a novel recycling process for the cells developed in SPINMATE. The definition of the recycling process flow is based on a literature review on recycling processes potentially suitable for the chemistry and characteristics of the developed cells, safety requirements and regulations, and on the inputs from the partners developing the cell materials in WP3. Results from the experimental activities will be presented in Deliverable 8.4. (D8.4. Report on experimental recycling process).

2. SPINMATE cell chemistry and characteristics

The possibilities for improving conventional liquid electrolyte-based lithium-ion battery (LIB) technology are reaching a limit. Thus, it is essential to explore alternative or next-generation technologies and carefully track their advancements. In this context, the ongoing development of new-generation solid-state batteries (SSBs) is noteworthy, as they demonstrate significant progress in various key performance indicators (KPIs) for batteries. This indicates a potential surge in their production in the years to come (1). The conventional LIBs and SSBs differ primarily in the nature of their electrolyte: in the LIBs the electrolyte is a liquid solution consisting of organic solvents (e.g., DMC, EMC, EC) and a conductive salt (e.g., LiPF_6), while in the case of SSBs, the electrolyte is in a solid phase. The solid electrolytes can be divided into different groups, including (i) oxide-based, (ii) sulfide-based, (iii) polymer-based or (iv) a combination of them. In SPINMATE, the solid electrolyte is a polymer-based material, composed of a Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-HP) polymer structure, ethyl carbonate (EC) as plasticizer, polyolefin (PO) as separator, and different conductive Li salts (i.e., LiFSI, LiBOB, LiPF_6 , LiNO_3).

Solid electrolytes offer several advantages compared to conventional liquid electrolytes used in LIBs. The main one is the absence of carbonates solvents, such as DMC or EMC. These organic solvents, commonly found in liquid electrolytes, are volatile, toxic, and highly flammable, potentially resulting in thermal runaways in the presence of sparks or elevated temperatures (2). Solid electrolytes have therefore inherently higher thermal stability compared to liquid electrolytes, reducing the risk of thermal runaway and fire hazards associated with LIBs (3). They also exhibit better stability and lower reactivity towards certain electrode materials (e.g., Li metal anode), resulting in improved cycle life and reduced capacity degradation over repeated charge-discharge cycles and have a wider electrochemical stability window, allowing for the utilization of higher voltage electrode materials, such as lithium metal (LiM) anodes, which further enhances the energy density and performance of SSBs (4). Furthermore, they show promise in inhibiting the formation of lithium dendrites, which are finger-like growths that can cause short circuits and safety hazards in LIBs (5). Polymer-based electrolyte also show some advantages compared with other kind of solid electrolytes, specially sulfide-based electrolytes. Sulfide-based electrolytes are chemically instable in ambient conditions: they can undergo chemical reactions with moisture

and carbon dioxide present in the environment, leading to degradation and the formation of unwanted solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) layers (6). Furthermore, their reaction with moisture produces sulfide hydrogen (H_2S) and extremely toxic compound. Table 1 shows the amount of H_2S generated from different types of sulfide-based electrolytes exposed in a humid environment. The values range between 0 ppm and 2×10^6 ppm, while the permissible exposure limit (PEL) for H_2S is 20 (7).

Table 1 - Amount of H_2S generated from different sulfide-based (8)

Electrolyte composition	Time exposure (s)	Amount of H_2S (ppm)
67Li ₂ S-33P ₂ S ₅	60	2,000,000
Li ₇ P ₃ S ₁₁	60	900,000
Li ₃ PS ₄	60	10,000
Li ₃ PS ₄	60	200,000
80Li ₂ S-20P ₂ S ₅	60	600,000
Li ₃ PS ₄	600	70,000
90 Li ₃ PS ₄ -10Fe ₂ O ₃	600	20,000
90 Li ₃ PS ₄ -10ZnO	600	0
90 Li ₃ PS ₄ -10Bi ₂ O ₃	600	0
17Li ₂ O-83Li ₇ P ₃ S ₁₁	60	<9,000
20Li ₂ O-80Li ₇ P ₃ S ₁₁	60	<10,000
25Li ₂ O-75Li ₇ P ₃ S ₁₁	60	<11,000
7Li ₂ O-93Li ₇ P ₃ S ₁₁	60	<12,000
75Li ₂ S-15P ₂ S ₅ -10P ₂ O ₅	60	1,200
30LiI-70(0.07Li ₂ O-0.68 Li ₂ S-0.25P ₂ S ₅)	60	9,000

In SPINMATE, the anode material will be LiM, a common anode active material (AAM) in SSB, with copper as the current collector. LiM has a high theoretical specific capacity of 3860 mAh/g (9) and low electrochemical potential, resulting in a higher cell voltage and improved energy density compared to other anode materials (10). However, LiM is a very unstable compound. It reacts exothermically in the presence of water forming hydrogen gas (H_2), a highly reacting fuel that violently reacts with oxygen. It is hence pivotal to take into account the inherent instability of this compound when designing a recycling process for SSBs to guarantee the safety of the procedure, as elucidated in Section 4.

The cathode active material (CAM) of the cells is NMC811 ($LiNi_{0.8}Mn_{0.1}Co_{0.1}O_2$). Currently, NMC LIBs are the dominant chemistry in the EV sector, due to the high energy density of the Ni-rich cells. This kind of cathode material contains valuable metals that can be recovered as salts during the recycling process. Figure 1 shows the structure of a SPINMATE monolayer cell.

Figure 1 - Structure of a SPINMATE monolayer cell.

3. LIBs recycling state-of-art overview

The European Union (EU) is fully dedicated to the fight against climate change by transitioning towards a sustainable, secure, and competitive energy system. Batteries are one of the keys to enabling technologies for the electrification of key sectors, including transport, power, and industry. This transition is expected to lead to a five-fold increase in global battery demand over the next decade, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Global battery demand

Source: Fastmarkets – ICBR Black mass pricing – Sept 2023

The substantial surge in global battery demand will inevitably lead to the generation of vast volumes of battery waste. This waste from the battery industry comprises two main types: end-of-life batteries (EoL), which are batteries reaching the end of their useful life, and production scrap, which is waste generated during the battery manufacturing process. A significant increase is anticipated in the production of both production scrap (Figure 3.a) and end-of-life batteries (Figure 3.b) in the upcoming years, with a particular emphasis on the latter (EoL).

Figure 3 - Forecast scrap production (a) and EoL LIBs generation (b)
 Source: *Fastmarkets – ICBR Black mass pricing – Sept 2023*

Even though, according to projections, significant volumes of EoL first-generation electric vehicle batteries are not anticipated until 2033, battery scrap will be generated during the production of the batteries. This type of battery waste is expected to be the main available waste for battery recyclers at least until the 2030s (Figure 4) (11).

Figure 4 EoL EV batteries and production scrap available for recycling
 Source: *Fastmarkets battery recycling and black mass outlook (11)*

As a result from the aforementioned the new Battery Regulation (12) incorporates specific recycling targets for battery waste, as it is presented in **Figure 5**. These targets are categorized into three distinct areas. Firstly, the recycling yield is addressed. By 2026, the overall recycling yield should reach a minimum of 65%, escalating to 70% by 2031. Secondly, specific material recovery targets are established for Li, Ni, Co, and Cu. By 2028, the goals are set at 50% for Li and 90% for the rest. Looking ahead to 2032, the targets increase to 80% for Li and 95% for Ni, Co,

and Cu. Lastly, a target is outlined for the recycled content in new batteries. By 2031, batteries should incorporate a minimum of 6% recycled Ni, and a 16% of recycled Co. By 2036, the aim is to achieve a 15% of recycled Ni, along with at least 26% of recycled materials Co and 12% of recycled Li.

Figure 5 - recycling targets set in the Battery Regulation

Considering the overall recycling yield of 70% target by 2031 and the other recycling targets from the Battery Regulation presented in Figure 5, the recycling and recovery targets of SPINMATE cells have been established (Table 2).

Table 2 Recycling targets for SPINMATE cells.

Component	Target (recovery rate (w/w%))
Solid-state electrolyte materials	>70%
Li metal anode	>70%
Ni	>95%
Mn	>95%
Co	>95%
Li	>70%
Al	>95%
Cu	>95%

The recycling of LIBs at industrial scale is typically divided in two stages: the pre-processing and the refining or downstream process (13). The combination of different preprocessing approaches and downstream techniques results in different recycling routes, as presented in Figure 6. There are two main possibilities for the pre-processing: mechanical pretreatment and pyrometallurgical pretreatment. In both cases, the refining or downstream process consists of a hydrometallurgical process for the recovery of valuable metals from the cathode material.

Figure 6- LIBs recycling routes

Mechanical pretreatment:

Prior to the mechanical pretreatment, the batteries must be fully discharged to avoid a potential runaway during the process. The mechanical process typically starts with the shredding of the batteries under inert conditions (i.e., nitrogen or vacuum) (13). After shredding, a drying step takes place to remove the electrolyte carbonate solvents. During the drying, physical mixing is typically applied to deagglomerate the shredded material and to enhance the delamination of the active material from the current collectors. The shreds fraction with the finest particle size (<100 μm), called ‘black mass’, contains liberated active particles of lithium transition metal oxides (LMOs) and graphite particles. This fine fraction can be separated from the rest of the dried shredded material by particle size separation (i.e., sieving). The rest of dried shreds, can be further separated into the aluminum, copper, ferrous and plastics fractions by different physical-based separation techniques (density, magnetic, particle size) (14). The black mass can go directly to the hydrometallurgical process, or after a thermal treatment to remove remaining organics and other impurities.

Pyrometallurgical process:

The pyrometallurgical approach involves employing thermal processes to recover valuable metals from battery waste. There are two main options within the pyrometallurgical process: roasting and smelting (15).

In roasting, certain pretreatments are necessary prior to the calcination step, including discharge and dismantling. The dismantling is achieved either manually or via a mechanical destructive process that involves shredding and sorting operations. Subsequently, a thermal pretreatment is applied to remove the liquid electrolyte, along with various organic compounds like the organic binder and conductive carbon. Following the thermal pretreatment for organic compound removal, the remaining solid residue containing the CAM is incinerated in conjunction with reducing agents, leading to metals reduction, and yielding a carbon residue and a metals-rich alloy. The alloy is then subjected to further refinement.

On the other hand, the smelting approach does not require any pretreatments. Because the high temperatures used in the process render potential hazards inactive, batteries can be directly fed into the melting furnace. The smelting process typically occurs in two steps. In the first step, a low-temperature process is applied to evaporate and recover the electrolyte and other carbon-containing compounds. Then in the second step, the valuable metals are concentrated into a molten alloy phase and further recovered through leaching.

The pyrometallurgical approach proves suitable for Co- and Ni-rich cell chemistries, as these materials can be effectively recovered. However, the recovery of lithium is less efficient, as it tends to be lost in the slag that is generated during the pyrometallurgical process. Additionally, the process demands significant energy and leaves a substantial environmental footprint (16).

Hydrometallurgical process:

The hydrometallurgical approach is based on the extraction of valuable metals from the battery waste into a liquid phase, allowing for their selective recovery. The hydrometallurgical process can be applied to either the black mass derived from the mechanical process or the alloy and slag produced from the pyro-process

Different types of leaching agents can be used to dissolve the metals, and different parameters such as pH, residence time, temperature, solid/liquid ratio, or rotational speed can be optimized to selectively leach target elements. After the leaching, the metals can be recovered by different techniques, including solvent extraction, ion-exchange recovery or selective precipitation. The hydrometallurgical process typically involves the use of strong acids and generates high volumes of waste streams.

Alternative approach: direct recycling

One alternative to the industrial-scale recycling approaches is the direct recycling. Unlike the hydrometallurgical process, which is based on the breakdown of the CAM into its individual precursors, the direct recycling is based on the healing of the spent CAM (17). The healing process consist on the recovery of the stoichiometry by compensating the Li deficiency, while maintaining the crystalline structure of the CAM (figure 7). There are different techniques that can be applied to heal the cathode material, including hydrothermal, solid-thermal and electrochemical approaches (17).

Figure 7 - Relithiation process scheme

The direct recycling is an economically attractive alternative to the hydro process, because the value of the CAM is higher than the sum of its individual precursors (Figure 8). This difference in the value between the CAM and the precursors is specially significant for Co-,Ni-free chemistries such as LFP. Moreover, the direct recycling shows some advantages compare to hydro-/pyro-approaches in terms of energy consumption and environmental impact, an offer a closed-loop approach by avoiding the energy-consuming resynthesis of the CAM after the recovery of the metal salts (18).

Figure 8 - CAM vs constituents cost
 Source: *The ReCell Center* (52)

The main limitation of direct recycling comes from the fact that in order to be able to apply the healing process, the CAM material must meet a certain level of purity, which is incompatible with mechanical pre-processing, which typically leads to cross-contamination. It means that for the direct recycling to work, the cathode must be manually disassembled and purified before applying the healing process. It makes it very difficult to upscale the process due to the heterogeneity of battery modules and cell configurations, hindering the automation of the disassembly process to the electrode level, and limiting the direct recycling to the lab-scale.

4. SSBs recycling

Dealing with SSBs presents a unique set of challenges and limitations when it comes to recycling technologies. In the case of Spinmate cells, the absence of sulfide materials reduces the hazards during the recycling process due the formation of H_2S , but it is necessary to consider the reactivity of the LiM and the effect of the recycling process on the polymer electrolyte. As explained in the previous section, state-of-art recycling technologies for LIBs at industrial scale include mechanical, thermal and hydrometallurgical processes. These processes are suitable for LIBs with conventional liquid electrolyte and graphite-based anode, however, they present some limitations when dealing with solid electrolytes and LiM as anode. The main limitations of state-of-art recycling methods for SSBs are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 - SoA LIBs recycling processes and limitations for SSBs

Process	Conventional LIBs	Limitations for SPINMATE SSBs
Mechanical pre-process	Shredding under nitrogen atmosphere	LiM reactivity with water and nitrogen.
	Liquid electrolyte recovery via evaporation/condensation	Solid electrolyte: evaporation approach not feasible.
	Physical separation of shreds	Chemical separation is required due to the adhesive nature of Li metal and the presence of solid electrolyte.
Pyrometallurgical process	Alloy containing valuable metals + Li containing slag	Material trapped in slag.
		Burnt polymer-based electrolyte.
		Generation of toxic gases (organics, HF).
Hydrometallurgical process	Recovery of valuable metals from alloy or black mass	Reactivity of LiM with water.

Mechanical Pre-processing:

1. Reactive Atmosphere for Shredding: Shredding SSBs appears feasible, since it takes place in a tight, closed system, with an inert atmosphere, but the reactive nature of metallic lithium poses challenges. Li reacts vigorously, especially with water, so it is crucial to ensure that the shredding takes place in a dry atmosphere. While conventional processes use a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent thermal runaway, nitrogen reacts with Li, producing Li nitride (figure 9) (19)). Exploring alternative inert atmospheres becomes hence imperative.

Figure 9 - Li metal reaction with nitrogen
 Source: Yamaguchi et al., 2017 (19)

2. Electrolyte recovery: In conventional recycling processes for LIBs, a drying step is typically employed to collect the liquid electrolyte through evaporation under vacuum, followed by condensation. However, this approach is not applicable to SPINMATE cells, as their electrolyte does not consist of liquid solvents but rather a solid polymer structure. Chemical separation

based on dissolution and precipitation of the polymer structure might be a possible solution, which will be further explained in the next section (4.1 *Potential recycling approaches*).

3. Separation of shredded materials: Post-shredding, the adhesive nature of Li metal complicates physical separation (20). As in the case of the solid electrolyte, chemical separation via LiM conversion might be required, a topic that will be further explained in the next section.

Pyrometallurgical Process:

1. Material Trapping in Slag: A significant limitation in pyrometallurgical processes lies in the trapping of materials from SSBs, including Li metal and sulfide and oxide-based electrolytes, within the slag. Retrieving these trapped materials becomes impractical, leading to substantial losses.

2. Burnt Polymer-Based Electrolyte: In the case of polymer-based electrolytes, burning occurs without the possibility of recovery. This limitation poses a challenge as it results in the irreversible loss of valuable components.

3. Generation of Toxic Gases: The pyrometallurgical route generates organic toxic gases, posing environmental and safety concerns. Furthermore, the thermal decomposition of the PVDF-based electrolyte results in the generation of HF (21) (22), a very toxic and corrosive compound. Managing and mitigating the emission of these harmful by-products becomes crucial in the recycling process.

Hydrometallurgical Process:

1. Reactivity of LiM: The hydrometallurgical process holds promise for recovering valuable compounds from cathode materials due to similar chemistries. However, the reactivity of Li metal with the aqueous solutions used in the leaching process demands careful consideration. Balancing efficient recovery with the potential reactivity challenges becomes a key aspect of this method.

In conclusion, navigating the recycling landscape for solid-state batteries involves addressing these intricate challenges within each recycling technology. The pursuit of sustainable and effective solutions requires a nuanced understanding of the materials and processes involved in the realm of solid-state battery recycling.

4.1 Potential recycling approaches

As it can be derived from the previous section, the state of the art recycling processes available for conventional LIBs with liquid electrolyte cannot be directly applied on solid state batteries. New processes must be developed and current processes must be adapted to the chemistry of the SSBs. Different processes will be proposed for the individual cell components: Li metal anode, polymer electrolyte, and CAM.

2 different approaches will be considered for the recycling of the batteries, to first assess the proposed processes on the individual cell materials, and then as a part of a continuous process applied on all components mixed together.

Approach 1 will be based on manual disassembly of the cells (Figure 10). The cells will be opened under inert atmosphere of Argon. The cathode material (NMC coated on Al foil), solid electrolyte

(polymer membrane) and anode (Li metal foil and Cu current collector) will be manually separated from each other and treated individually.

Figure 10 - Manual disassembly approach scheme

In Approach 2 (Figure 11), mechanical preprocessing to shred the cells will be conducted in collaboration with TUBS. TUBS will contribute with its experience in shredding SSB materials under an inert atmosphere. Techniques initially assessed on manually disassembled cell components will be then applied to the shredded material. Different innovative methods will be explored during the shredding, such as the selection of different kinds of atmosphere inside the shredding chamber.

Figure 11 - Mechanical pre-processing approach scheme

- **Li metal conversion**

In the realm of lithium metal (LiM) recycling, it is noteworthy that while there are some companies that focus on neutralizing LiM before disposal and landfilling without addressing the recovery of lithium, there are just a few companies addressing the recycling of LiM, specifically derived from lithium metal scrap rather than solid-state batteries.

Toxco, a recycling company based in Canada, patented a recycling process suitable for the recovery of lithium from lithium metal scrap (23). The process begins with a cryogenic pre-process to lower the material's temperature and reduce its reactivity. Subsequently, the cooled material undergoes crushing in an aqueous caustic solution. This reaction generates hydrogen and heat, leading to the ignition of hydrogen and the combustion of all organic impurities. The resulting material then undergoes a hydrometallurgical process where lithium is precipitated as lithium carbonate.

Building upon the Toxco process, Cardarelli et al. (24) patented a process for the recovery of lithium and vanadium from solid-state batteries with lithium metal anode and polymer-based electrolyte, similar to those developed in SPINMATE. Notably, this patent is the only one identified for this battery type. The process, which is shown in Figure 12, starts with a cooling step to harden the soft materials to facilitate comminution and reduce the reactivity of unstable compounds. Then, a cryogenic shredding takes place, by feeding a cutting mill with argon. The resulting slurry is then fed into an incineration vessel, where the argon is evaporated, and the shredded heated up to 1000K. The dried shreds enter then a digestion tank, where Li is converted to Li sulphate, and selectively recovered in a hydrometallurgical process.

Figure 12 - Patented process scheme for Li metal recovery from LiM-polymer cells

Even though this process is tailored for solid state batteries with a similar chemistry than SPINMATE cells, it's worth noting that this patented process concentrates on the recovery of lithium and vanadium, excluding the recovery of other materials such as the polymer-based electrolyte, which is incinerated during a thermal process. The primary objective of our project is to propose a recovery process for LiM that aligns with the simultaneous recovery of the solid electrolyte. To achieve this goal, our proposed solution involves stabilizing and solubilizing lithium by converting LiM to Li salts.

In the limited body of literature dedicated to lithium metal conversion, researchers have delineated two primary methodologies: oxidation to yield Li_2O and carbonation to generate Li_2CO_3 (25). These transformative reactions are typically accomplished through thermal treatments conducted in environments abundant in either oxygen (O_2) or carbon dioxide (CO_2). The oxidation process involves the creation of a protective Li oxide layer on the surface of LiM, acting as a barrier to prevent complete metal oxidation. However, prior to oxidation, a crucial mechanical pretreatment is essential, necessitating the crushing of LiM into fine particles to expose it to oxygen adequately, ensuring a thorough conversion. Importantly, this crushing process must occur under an inert atmosphere to prevent the ignition of Li metal due to moisture presence.

An alternate pathway for LiM conversion involves its reaction with CO_2 , leading to the formation of Li carbonate, as elucidated by Zhuang et al. (26) in their exploration of interactions between Li metal and CO_2 . In the realm of LiM- CO_2 batteries, a stable solid electrolyte interface comprising Li carbonate is established through the reaction between metallic lithium and CO_2 (27).

Diverging from the traditional thermal carbonation process, researchers have explored the Li carbonation process by reacting Li with supercritical CO_2 (28) - a state of CO_2 exhibiting properties of both a gas and a liquid. Supercritical CO_2 , characterized by low viscosity and high diffusivity, facilitates efficient penetration into porous solid matrices. However, a significant drawback emerges with the potential presence of moisture within the system, which may induce an exothermic reaction with LiM.

Upon closer examination of the reaction mechanisms between LiM and CO₂ at room temperature, it becomes apparent that the conversion pathway does not directly yield Li carbonate; rather, the predominant product is Li oxalate (Li₂C₂O₄) (29). Zhuang et al. (26) conducted a comprehensive study on the reaction mechanism of Li with CO₂ across varying temperatures (120-320K). Their findings highlighted the emergence of Li oxalate as an intermediate species preceding the formation of Li carbonate (Li₂CO₃).

Li oxalate exhibits notable solubility in water, surpassing that of Li carbonate, as elucidated in Table 4. Subjecting Li oxalate to high temperatures triggers its thermal decomposition, resulting in the production of Li carbonate and CO.

Table 4 – Solubility of Li salts in water at room temperature

Compound	Solubility in water (20°C)
Li₂CO₃	13.3 g/L (30)
Li₂C₂O₄	66 g/L (31)

In SPINMATE, lithium metal will undergo treatment with CO₂ gas to facilitate its conversion into lithium oxalate. The process will utilize a vacuum furnace as a reactor to ensure an environment devoid of air or moisture within the furnace chamber. Operating at room temperature is crucial to prevent the thermal decomposition of lithium oxalate. The system will be purged with CO₂, promoting the LiM reaction into lithium oxalate. Subsequently, the lithium oxalate salt can be leached with water and then precipitated as lithium carbonate. This conversion process will be applied to manually disassembled Li metal foils, shredded Li metal foils, and shredded cells containing Li metal mixed with other cell components. TUBS and ABEE will collaborate on the mechanical preprocessing, which will expose the entire surface of the metallic lithium foil to prevent the formation of protective layers that may impede the complete conversion of LiM.

Additionally, TUBS and ABEE will investigate the conversion of LiM during the shredding process. The optimal conversion conditions determined in the vacuum oven will serve as a reference to establish the operational conditions for shredding in the cutting mill, which is designed to operate under the desired atmosphere. Figure 13 illustrates the recovery process proposed for the LiM.

Figure 13 - LiM conversion process scheme

- **Electrolyte recovery**

The solid electrolyte of SPINMATE cells consists of a solid polymer comprising PVDF-HFP, ethylene carbonate (EC) as a plasticizer, and various lithium conductive salts such as LiFSI, LiBOB, LiPF₆, LiNO₃, along with polyolefins (PO) serving as separators. The electrolyte recovery process proposed aims to extract the PVDF-HFP structure and all possible components from the rest of the electrolyte materials.

The PVDF is a component present in conventional LIBs, typically used as a binder. The PVDF is not recovered in conventional recycling processes. Instead, it is burnt during a thermal process at high temperature (up to 1000C). Physical separation, taking advantage of some physical properties which differentiate this material from the rest of cell components, might be an option for recovery. However, this approach doesn't seem feasible due to the adhesive nature of the polymer and Li metal compounds. One potential approach for the recovery of the polymer electrolyte is by means of a solvent-based process, comprising the dissolution of the PVDF-HFP in a suitable solvent, and the further precipitation to recover it again as a solid. Table 5 shows the potential solvents identified in literature for the dissolution of the PVDF-HFP structure:

Table 5– Potential solvents for PVDF-HFP

Solvent	References
NMP	Sliz et al., 2022 (32)
DMF	Marshall et al., 2021 (33); Sliz et al., 2022 (32)
DMSO	Lin et al., 2023 (34); Sliz et al., 2022 (32)
Cyrene	Marino et al., 2019 (35); Bai et al., 2020 (36)

N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) stands out as the most widely utilized solvent for PVDF dissolution (32). This dipolar aprotic solvent finds application in the formulation of cathode slurries during battery manufacturing processes, effectively dissolving PVDF – a common binder for cathodes in conventional lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). However, despite its efficacy, NMP presents certain drawbacks. Notably, it boasts a high boiling point (approximately 200C), leading

to an energy-intensive recovery process through evaporation. Additionally, its low autoignition point (around 250°C) raises safety concerns. Moreover, NMP is characterized by its toxicity and considerable environmental impact, prompting expectations of restricted usage due to evolving regulations on toxic solvents. Consequently, there is ongoing research dedicated to exploring alternative solvents capable of efficiently dissolving PVDF.

Dimethylformamide (DMF) is another polar aprotic solvent investigated for PVDF dissolution, offering a potential alternative to NMP (32). As a polar aprotic solvent, DMF shares similarities with NMP, exhibiting comparable polarity and dielectric constant, and its efficiency in dissolving PVDF is on par with that of NMP. Notably, DMF surpasses NMP in certain aspects, featuring a lower boiling point (155°C) and a higher autoignition temperature (445°C) (33). Despite these advantages, DMF presents the same issues as NMP in terms of toxicity.

Another solvent that has been observed to dissolve PVDF is dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (32) (34). Similar to DMF, DMSO boasts a low boiling point (190°C) and a high autoignition temperature (300°C) (32). On top of these characteristics, DMSO distinguishes itself by presenting low toxicity compared to NMP and DMF. This additional attribute positions DMSO a compelling candidate for further evaluation as a solvent agent in the recovery of PVDF-HFP.

An eco-friendly alternative to the aforementioned solvents is Cyrene, a bio-based organic compound known for its reduced environmental impact, safety, and extended life cycle as a solvent agent (37). There are a few studies (35) (36) that have evaluated the suitability of Cyrene as a solvent for PVDF, positioning it as a promising contender for PVDF-HFP recovery alongside DMSO.

In the SPINMATE recycling process, both Cyrene and DMSO will be assessed for the dissolution and recovery of the PVDF-HFP structure. Following the dissolution phase, centrifugation might be required to separate the solution from the solid residue, based on previous in-house experiments performed by ABEE to dissolve PVDF binder from conventional LIBs using different kind of solvents.

The residual material will contain lithium salts, ethylene carbonate (EC), and polyolefines (PO). To extract the lithium conductive salts, the solid residue will undergo a washing process using carbonate solvents commonly found in liquid electrolytes, such as dimethyl carbonate (DMC) and ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC). Recovery of EC will involve evaporation and condensation, which will be done by using a vacuum oven equipped with an integrated condensing system. The use of a vacuum oven is required to lower the vapor temperature of EC, whose boiling point at atmospheric pressure is 248°C (38). Examining the vapor pressure curve for EC reveals that, even at a vacuum of 5 mbar, the temperature needs to be elevated above 100°C for effective evaporation (39). It is crucial to note that the thermal decomposition of the lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) conductive salt occurs above 80°C (40). Therefore, the recovery of lithium salts must precede the EC evaporation process to prevent the formation of hydrofluoric acid (HF). The overall recovery process is presented in Figure 14.

The dissolution and washing processes outlined will initially be implemented on the isolated electrolyte membrane and subsequently extended to the shreds containing a mixture of various cell components.

Figure 14 - Electrolyte recovery process scheme

- **Downstream process for cathode materials recovery**

The cathode material is composed of NMC and an aluminum (Al) current collector. The hydrometallurgical process aims to extract individual metals in salt form from the NMC, which can then be utilized as precursors for the re-synthesis of CAM.

This hydrometallurgical procedure encompasses leaching and selective recovery stages. During leaching, the constituents of CAM transition from a solid matrix to a liquid phase, enabling selective recovery. In the project, a combination of ion-exchange, solvent extraction, and selective precipitation will be employed post-leaching to selectively recover Nickel (Ni), Cobalt (Co), Manganese (Mn), and Lithium (Li).

Preceding leaching, the cathode must undergo delamination from the current collector. For that, the Al current collector must be dissolved in a solvent inert to CAM (e.g., NaOH). After drying, NMC powder can undergo leaching.

Various acid/base leaching solutions will be assessed, alongside different process parameters such as solution molar concentration, solid/liquid ratio, rotational speed, pH, temperature, and residence time. These parameters will be fine-tuned to identify the most suitable leaching solution.

Post-leaching, the resulting Pregnant Liquid Solution (PLS) will undergo different routes:

- i) Ion exchange and ii) solvent extraction, in combination with selective precipitation of the target metals.

Figure 15 illustrates the general process flow scheme for the hydrometallurgical recovery process.

Figure 15 - Downstream process flow scheme

Solvent extraction:

Solvent extraction (SX) is a mature technology used for the selective recovery of valuable metals from liquid solutions (41). The process consists of the transfer of the valuable metal contained in an aqueous solution, into an organic phase, which is known as extractant. After the extraction, there is a step called scrubbing, which consists of the removal of other metal impurities present in the organic phase. After the scrubbing, the stripping process takes place, where the extracted metal is returned to an aqueous solution from which it can be precipitated.

Many different routes can be found in literature for the recovery of the valuable metals contained in NMC LIBs using solvent extraction after the leaching. The selection of the extractant depends on the composition and pH of the PLS. There are different kinds of extractants, including acidic, basic, solvating and ionic liquids (IL). Table 6 summarize the most common extractants used for the recovery of NMC metals and their potential hydrometallurgical routes.

In SPINMATE, depending on the PLS media and its composition, the most suitable extractant will be selected, and the most efficient route and operational conditions will be implemented based on the reported results from the literature research.

Table 6 - List of extractants and potential recovery routes

Extractant		Route	References
Acidic	Cyanex 272	1.Extraction of Mn using D2EHPA 2. Extraction of Co using Cyanex 272 3. Selective precipitation of Ni, Li	Granata et al., 2012 (42)
	PC-88A	1. Selective precipitation of Mn 2. Extraction of Co using PC-88A 3. Extraction of Ni (from Li+Ni raffinate) using 0.15MPC88A	Chen et al., 2011 (43) Nguyen et al., 2014 (44)
	D2EHPA	1. Selective Ni precipitation (using DMG) 2. Extraction of Mn using D2EHPA 3. Consecutive precipitation of Co and Li.	Chen et al., 2015 (45)
Basic	Almine 336	1. Extraction of Co using Almine 336 2. Selective Ni precipitation 3. Consecutive precipitation Mn, Li	Fernandes et al., 2013 (46)
	TOA	1. Extraction of Co using TOA 2. Selective precipitation (high efficiency, but lower selectivity than Almine 336)	Torkaman et al., 2017 (47)
Solvating	Cyanex 923	1. Extraction of Co, Ni and Mn 2. Selective scrubbing of Ni (using MgCl ₂) 3. Selective stripping of Ni and Mn (using NaNO ₃)	Larsson and Binnemans., 2015 (48)

Ion exchange:

Ion exchange is a promising technique for the recovery of battery metals, in which ions in a solution are replaced by ions of a similar charge from an insoluble solid (resin) phase.

The choice of ion-exchange resins depends on their selectivity for the desired metals. In the PLS containing Ni, Mn, Co, and Li, selective resins will be employed for Ni, Mn, and Co recovery, as there are currently no commercially available resins that selectively recover Li. Consequently, Ni, Co, and Mn will be recovered first, leaving Li in the final solution, where it can be precipitated as Li₂CO₃.

Considering resin selectivity and availability, Lewatit TP260 (49) (amino methyl phosphonic acid Chelating Resin), Lewatit TP220 (50) (bispicolylamine Chelating Resin), and Lewatit TP208 (51) (Iminodiacetic acid Chelating Resin) have been considered for the ion-exchange process. Table 6 provides an overview of the selectivity of these resins towards different elements.

Table 7 - Resins selected for the ion-exchange process

Resin	Selectivity
Lewatit TP260	Cu > Zn > Ni > Co >> Ca > Mg >>> Na
Lewatit TP220	Ni > Fe > Co
Lewatit TP208	Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Fe (II) > Mn >> Ca > Mg >>> Na

Lewatit TP260 is selective towards Ni and Co. It can be used in a first step to separate the Ni and Co from the Li and Mn, which will remain in the solution. Then, Lewatit TP220 can be used to separate Ni from Co, since it is more selective towards Ni. For the PLS containing the Mn and Li, Lewatit TP208 can be used to selectively recover the Mn, while Li will remain alone in the solution. All the isolated metals can be then precipitated by using different methods.

4.2 Recycling process flow definition

As detailed in preceding sections, two distinct approaches are planned for the recycling of SPINMATE cells.

Approach 1 is based on the manual disassembly of the SPINMATE cells. The manual disassembly will result in three separate streams: the anode material, including the LiM and the Cu current collector, the polymer-based electrolyte, and the cathode material, including the NMC material and the Al current collector. Each component will undergo a tailored treatment process.

For the Li metal, the conversion to Li oxalate by reaction with CO₂ is being studied. Two different routes will be considered: the reaction in a vacuum furnace under a dry atmosphere, and the reaction during shredding under CO₂-rich atmosphere.

The recovery of the electrolyte will occur in different stages. First, the PVDF-HFP will be dissolved in a suitable and sustainable solvent, which will be then evaporated to recover the PVDF-HFP polymer. The non-soluble fraction, containing the Li conductive salts and the plasticizer (EC), will be washed with carbonate solvents to recover the conductive salts. The collection of EC via evaporation under vacuum and condensation will also be studied.

Finally, a hydrometallurgical process will be applied for the recovery of the valuable metals from the NMC CAM. The process starts with delamination from the current collector, followed by leaching to transfer the valuable metals from the NMC powder into a liquid solution. Then, two different routes will be assessed for the selective recovery of the metals: solvent extraction and ion exchange. Figure 16 shows the overall process flow diagram (PFD) of Approach 1.

In Approach 2, the initial phase involves a mechanical pre-treatment wherein the cells are shredded, followed by the integration of all processes studied on individual cell components in Approach 1 into a continuous process flow. Two distinct shredding processes are considered: one under a dry, inert atmosphere (Approach 2.a) and the other with a CO₂-rich atmosphere (Approach 2.b), aiming to investigate LiM conversion during shredding. After the LiM conversion into a stable and soluble compound, the electrolyte recovery process will take place. As explained in Approach 1, the PVDF-HFP will be first dissolved. However, In this case, the solid residue will contain the Li conductive salts and the EC, together with the converted Li from the anode, and with the cathode material. The solid stream will be washed with the carbonate solvents, and then dried under vacuum for the recovery of the EC. The dried stream, containing the anode and

cathode materials, will then proceed through the hydrometallurgical process, where the current collectors, the Li from the anode, and the valuable metals from the NMC cathode will be selectively recovered. Figure 17 shows the overall process flow of Approaches 2.a and 2.b.

Approach 1:

Figure 16 - Recycling process flow diagram based on manual disassembly approach

Approach 2.a

Approach 2.b

Figure 17 - Recycling process flow diagram of Approach 2.a and 2.b

5. Conclusion

This report exposes the critical necessity of designing a tailored recycling solution for the developed cells in this project. This need arises from the recently introduced Battery Regulation, which outlines explicit targets for battery recycling, including overall recycling yield, material recovery, and the integration of recycled materials into new batteries. The urgency stems from the anticipated battery waste that is expected to be generated in the coming years.

From the research presented in this deliverable, it can be inferred that the next-generation batteries developed in this project will not be ready for recycling until several years post-commercialization. However, during the battery production phase, the generation of scrap, including malfunctioning batteries, highlights the necessity for recycling technologies. Furthermore, compliance with the Battery Regulation underscores the crucial requirement for efficient recycling technologies to be readily available for the batteries entering the market

Another significant finding from this report is that the existing recycling technologies are unsuitable for the next generation of solid-state batteries. Consequently, adaptation of current methods and the development of new, cell chemistry-specific recycling techniques is imperative.

This deliverable proposes two recycling process flow alternatives: one based on manual disassembly and another on mechanical shredding. Manual disassembly offers the advantage of isolating different cell components without cross-contamination. However, it has drawbacks concerning operator safety and scalability. Manual disassembly, being time-consuming, is unsuitable for industrial-scale recycling when dealing with large quantities of cells. Although automated disassembly could be an option, this approach is still at a low Technology Readiness Level (TRL), which is attributed to the wide variety in cell, module, and pack designs and configurations.

It was found that a viable alternative is the mechanical pre-processing. The project will study a recycling process approach involving the shredding of cells and integrating processes assessed in the manual disassembled cell components. Collaborating with TUB, this approach, similar to the current industrial-scale recycling of LIBs, facilitates the upscaling of the process by substituting manual disassembly with mechanical shredding.

All findings from this deliverable will serve as a base for the experimental task *T8.4. Experimental recycling process*.

6. References

1. Fraunhofer Institute. *Solid-State Battery Roadmap 2035+*. s.l. : Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, 2022.
2. *Flammability of Li-Ion Battery Electrolytes: Flash Point and Self-Extinguishing Time Measurements*. Hess, Steffen, Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, Margret e Wachtler, Mario. s.l. : Journal of The Electrochemical Society, 2015, Vol. 162.
3. *Thin, flexible sulfide-based electrolyte film and its interface engineering for high performance solid-state lithium metal batteries*. Liu, Hong, et al. s.l. : Chemical Engineering Journal, 2022, Vol. 430.
4. *Lithium battery chemistries enabled by solid-state electrolytes*. Manthiram, Arumugam, Yu, Xingwen e Wang, Shaofei. s.l. : Nature Reviews Materials, 2017, Vol. 2.
5. *Ultrathin two-dimensional atomic crystals as stable interfacial layer for improvement of lithium metal anode*. Yan, Kai, et al. s.l. : Nano Letters, 2014, Vol. 14.
6. *Recent advances in lithium-ion battery materials for improved electrochemical performance: A review*. Mahmud, Saifullah, et al. s.l. : Results in Engineering, 2022, Vol. 15.
7. New Jersey Department of Health. nj.gov. [Online] 2012. <https://nj.gov/health/eoh/rtkweb/documents/fs/1017.pdf>.
8. *Sulfide solid electrolytes for all-solid-state lithium batteries: Structure, conductivity, stability and application*. Chen, Shaojie, et al. s.l. : Energy Storage Materials, 2018, Vol. 14.
9. *Challenges for Rechargeable Li Batteries*. Goodenough, John B. e Kim, Youngsik. s.l. : Chemistry of Materials, 2010, Vol. 22.
10. *Lithium metal anodes for rechargeable batteries*. Xu, Wu, et al. s.l. : Energy & Environmental Science, 2014, Vol. 2.
11. Fastmarkets. Six key trends in the battery recycling market. *fastmarkets.com*. [Online] 19 de June de 2023. <https://www.fastmarkets.com/insights/six-key-trends-battery-recycling-market/#:~:text=Production%20scrap%20currently%20accounts%20for,and%20production%20scrap%20for%2041%25..>
12. European Comission. *REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC*. s.l. : European Parliament, 2023.
13. Heimes, Heiner Hans, et al. *RECYCLING OF LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES*. s.l. : RWTH Aachen University, 2023.
14. *A review of physical processes used in the safe recycling of lithium ion batteries*. Sommerville, Roberto, et al. s.l. : Sustainable Materials and Technologies, 2020, Vol. 25.
15. *Pyrometallurgical options for recycling spent lithium-ion batteries: A comprehensive review*. Makuza, Brian, et al. s.l. : Journal of Power Sources, 2021, Vol. 491.
16. *Life cycle assessment of recycling options for automotive Li-ion battery packs*. Kallitsis, Evangelos, Korre, Anna e Kelsall, Geoff H. s.l. : Journal of Cleaner Production, 2022, Vol. 371.

17. *Direct recycling of spent Li-ion batteries: Challenges and opportunities toward practical applications.* Wei, Gaolei, et al. 9, s.l. : iScience, 2023, Vol. 26.
18. *Evaluation of the sustainability of technologies to recycle spent lithium-ion batteries, based on embodied energy and carbon footprint.* Fahimi, Ario, et al. s.l. : Journal of Cleaner Production, 2022, Vol. 338.
19. *Nitrogen Dissociation via Reaction with Lithium Alloys.* Yamaguchi, Shotaro, et al. s.l. : ACS Omega, 2017.
20. *Recycling for All Solid-State Lithium-Ion Batteries.* Azhari, Luqman, et al. 6, s.l. : Matter, 2020, Vol. 3.
21. *Dehydrofluorination behavior of poly(vinylidene fluoride) during thermal treatment using calcium carbonate.* Tanaka, Futoshi, et al. s.l. : Thermochemica Acta, 2021, Vol. 702.
22. *Investigation of morphology, crystallinity, thermal stability, piezoelectricity and conductivity of PVDF nanocomposites reinforced with epoxy functionalized MWCNTs.* Begum, Saddiqa, et al. s.l. : Composites Science and Technology, 2021, Vol. 211.
23. McLaughlin, William J. *Method for the neutralization of hazardous materials.* 5345033 United States, 6 de September de 1994. Process.
24. Cardarelli, Francois e Dube, Jonathan. *METHOD FOR RECYCLING SPENT LITHIUM METAL POLYMER RECHARGEABLE BATTERIES AND RELATED MATERIALS.* 7,192,564 B2 United States, 20 de March de 2007. Process.
25. *Environmentally Friendly Recovery of Lithium from Lithium–Sulfur Batteries.* Schwich, Lilian e Friedrich, Bernd. s.l. : Metals, 2022, Vol. 12.
26. *The reaction of lithium with carbon dioxide studied by photoelectron spectroscopy.* Zhuang, Guorong, Chen, Yufeng e Jr., Philip N Ross. 1, s.l. : Surface Science, 1998, Vol. 418.
27. *Towards a stable Li–CO₂ battery: The effects of CO₂ to the Li metal anode.* Qiu, Feilong, et al. s.l. : Energy Storage Materials, 2020, Vol. 26.
28. *Early-Stage Recovery of Lithium from Tailored Thermal Conditioned Black Mass Part I: Mobilizing Lithium via Supercritical CO₂-Carbonation.* Schwich, Lilian, Schubert, Tom e Friedrich, Bernd. s.l. : Metals, 2021, Vol. 11.
29. *The development and prospect of lithium carbon dioxide battery.* Huaiyu, Lu, yanping, Qu e lei, Cao. s.l. : IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 2019, Vol. 218.
30. Merck. *merckmillipore.* [Online] [merckmillipore.com. https://www.merckmillipore.com/BE/fr/product/Lithium-carbonate,MDA_CHEM-105680.](https://www.merckmillipore.com/BE/fr/product/Lithium-carbonate,MDA_CHEM-105680)
31. Merck. *merckmillipore.* [merckmillipore.com.](https://www.merckmillipore.com/BE/fr/product/di-Lithium-oxalate,MDA_CHEM-822085?ReferrerURL=https%3A%2F%2Fen.wikipedia.org%2F) [Online] [https://www.merckmillipore.com/BE/fr/product/di-Lithium-oxalate,MDA_CHEM-822085?ReferrerURL=https%3A%2F%2Fen.wikipedia.org%2F.](https://www.merckmillipore.com/BE/fr/product/di-Lithium-oxalate,MDA_CHEM-822085?ReferrerURL=https%3A%2F%2Fen.wikipedia.org%2F)
32. *Suitable Cathode NMP Replacement for Efficient Sustainable Printed Li-Ion Batteries.* Sliz, Rafal, et al. s.l. : ACS Publications, 2022, Vol. 5.
33. *On the Solubility and Stability of Polyvinylidene Fluoride.* Marshall, Jean E., et al. s.l. : Polymers (Basel), 2021, Vol. 13.

34. *Preparation of PVDF/PMMA composite membrane with green solvent for seawater desalination by gap membrane distillation.* Lin, Yu-Xian, et al. s.l. : Journal of Membrane Science, 2023, Vol. 679.
35. *New frontiers in sustainable membrane preparation: Cyrene™ as green bioderived solvent.* Marino, T., et al. s.l. : Journal of Membrane Science, 2019, Vol. 580.
36. *Sustainable recycling of cathode scraps via Cyrene-based separation.* Bai, Yaocai, et al. s.l. : Sustainable Materials and Technologies, 2020, Vol. 25.
37. *Cyrene: A bio-based sustainable solvent for organic synthesis.* Kong, Dickson e Dolzhenko, Anton V. s.l. : Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy, 2022, Vol. 25.
38. NHI National Library of Medicine. PubChem. *pubchem.com*. [Online] <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Ethylene-carbonate>.
39. *Vapor Pressures and Thermophysical Properties of Ethylene Carbonate, Propylene Carbonate, γ -Valerolactone, and γ -Butyrolactone.* Pokorný, Václav, et al. s.l. : J. Chem. Eng. Data, 2017, Vol. 62.
40. *Thermal stability of LiPF₆ salt and Li-ion battery electrolytes containing LiPF₆.* Yang, Hui, Zhuang, Guorong V. e Jr., Philip N. Ross. s.l. : Journal of Power Sources, 2006, Vol. 161.
41. *Separation and recovery of cobalt and nickel from end of life products via solvent extraction technique: A review.* Alvial-Hein, Guillermo, Mahandra, Harshit e Ghahreman, Ahmad. s.l. : Journal of Cleaner Production, 2021, Vol. 297.
42. *Simultaneous recycling of nickel metal hydride, lithium ion and primary lithium batteries: Accomplishment of European Guidelines by optimizing mechanical pre-treatment and solvent extraction operations.* Granata, G., et al. s.l. : Journal of Power Sources, 2012, Vol. 212.
43. *Process for the recovery of cobalt oxalate from spent lithium-ion batteries.* Chen, L., et al. s.l. : Hydrometallurgy, 2011, Vol. 108.
44. *Selective recovery of cobalt, nickel and lithium from sulphate leachate of cathode scrap of Li-ion batteries using liquid-liquid extraction.* Nguyen, V.T., et al. s.l. : Met. Mater, 2014, Vol. 20.
45. *Hydrometallurgical recovery of metal values from sulfuric acid leaching liquor of spent lithium-ion batteries.* Chen, Xiangping, et al. s.l. : Waste Management, 2015, Vol. 38.
46. *Separation of nickel(II), cobalt(II) and lanthanides from spent Ni-MH batteries by hydrochloric acid leaching, solvent extraction and precipitation.* Fernandes, Aline, Afonso, Julio Carlos e Dutra, Achilles Junqueira Bourdot. s.l. : Hydrometallurgy, 2013, Vol. 133.
47. *Recovery of cobalt from spent lithium ion batteries by using acidic and basic extractants in solvent extraction process.* Torkaman, Rezvan, et al. s.l. : Separation and Purification Technology, 2017, Vol. 186.
48. *Metal Recovery from Nickel Metal Hydride Batteries Using Cyanex 923 in Tricaprylylmethylammonium Nitrate from Chloride Aqueous Media.* Larsson, Kristian e Binnemans, Koen. s.l. : Journal of Sustainable Metallurgy, 2015, Vol. 1.
49. LANXESS. LANXESS. *lanxess.com*. [Online] <https://lanxess.com/en-US/Products-and-Brands/Products/1/LEWATIT--MonoPlus-TP-260>.
50. —. LANXESS. *lanxess.com*. [Online] <https://lanxess.com/en-US/Products-and-Brands/Products/1/LEWATIT--MonoPlus-TP-220>.

51. —. LANXESS. *lanxess.com*. [Online] <https://lanxess.com/en-US/Products-and-Brands/Products/1/LEWATIT--MonoPlus-TP-208>.
52. Spangenberg, Jeff. The ReCell Center: Making Lithium ion Battery Recycling Profitable. *Illinois Library*. [Online] 25 de March de 2021. <https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/items/117423>.